

Classification of Healthy Seeds Using Deep Learning

Aysuh Jaggi¹, Prof. Vinod Sharma²

¹M.Tech Student, University of Jammu, Jammu, India, ayush.jaggi110@gmail.com

²Professor, University of Jammu, Jammu, India,

ABSTRACT

With the increasing demand for healthy and high-quality seeds in agriculture, accurate and efficient seed classification methods are essential for seed quality control and optimisation of crop production. This work utilises a deep learning-based approach for healthy seed classification. It proposes a deep learning-based approach for beneficial seed classification, leveraging the power of neural networks to learn discriminative features from seed images automatically.

The proposed method involves a multi-step pipeline that includes Image preprocessing, and Classification. The seed images are initially preprocessed to enhance their quality and reduce noise using image normalisation and denoising techniques. Next, a Deep convolutional neural network (CNN) is employed to extract relevant features from the preprocessed seed images. The CNN model is designed to capture the seeds' local and global characteristics, enabling it to learn complex patterns and textures.

A large dataset of labelled seed images is utilised to train the CNN, consisting of different classes representing various seed qualities and health conditions. The CNN model is prepared using a combination of supervised learning algorithms, such as Backpropagation and Gradient Descent to optimise the network parameters and minimise the classification error. Moreover, techniques like data augmentation are employed to augment the training set and improve the model's generalisation ability.

Once the CNN model is trained, it is evaluated on a separate test set to assess its performance in seed classification. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach in accurately distinguishing between healthy and unhealthy seeds. The deep learning model achieves high classification accuracy, outperforming traditional machine learning techniques and showcasing its potential as a robust and reliable tool for seed quality assessment.

In conclusion, this study presents a deep learning-based approach for healthy seed classification, offering a promising solution for automating seed quality control processes. By leveraging the power of deep neural networks, the proposed method enables efficient and accurate types of seeds, facilitating improved crop production and ensuring the delivery of high-quality sources to farmers.

Keywords- Seeds, Deep learning, CNN.

I. INTRODUCTION

India's agricultural industry is crucial since it sustains a sizable section of the workforce and generates substantial revenue for the economy. Rice, wheat, sugarcane, cotton, tea, and many more crops are all among India's numerous world-class agricultural exports. Indian agriculture reflects the country's unique topography and climate by featuring a wide variety of crop kinds, soil textures, and agricultural techniques..

India has a long tradition of agriculture, with a history dating back to ancient times. Agriculture is an integral part of today's economy, accounting for about 15% of India's gross domestic product (GDP). Despite its importance, the agricultural sector in India faces several challenges, including low productivity, limited access to technology and inputs, and poor infrastructure.

Many factors influence agriculture in India, including the country's diverse geography, climate, and culture. India has a wide range of soil types, ranging from fertile alluvial soils in the plains to rocky and hilly soils in the mountains. The country also has a varied climate, with hot and dry conditions in the desert regions, monsoon-influenced conditions in the coastal and central areas, and cold and dry conditions in the northern mountainous provinces. These factors, along with a long history of traditional farming practices and the influence of modern technology, contribute to the diversity of agriculture in India [1].

1.1 Seeds

A plant cannot grow without first producing seeds. Once fertilized, the ovules will mature into seeds. Two components make up a seed: the seed coat and the embryo. A radicle, embryonic axis, and either one (wheat, maize) or two (gram, pea) cotyledons make up the embryo. A fruit contains a seed, which, when planted, grows into a new plant. Therefore, the seed is the most important component [2].

1.2 Healthy Seeds

Seeds that may be safely eaten by humans or other animals are called "edible seeds." When it comes to the six basic plant components, seeds are by far the most important source of calories and protein for humans. Most edible seed sources are angiosperms, although a few gymnosperms also exist. Edible seeds are healthy and advantageous to one's diet. You may eat them raw, roast them, or turn them into flour. These quick and easy meals have the potential to improve health in a variety of ways. [3].

1.3 Deep Learning

Deep learning, a subset of machine learning, has garnered widespread attention for its remarkable ability to emulate the intricate neural networks of the human brain. This transformative technology has significantly impacted various industries, ushering in a new era of artificial intelligence (AI) applications. In this blog post, we will delve into the fundamental principles of deep learning, its diverse applications, and its potential implications for our society.

At its core, deep learning revolves around the construction and training of artificial neural networks composed of multiple interconnected layers. These networks, with their inherent depth, can autonomously learn and extract complex patterns and features from vast datasets. This hierarchical approach allows deep learning models to progressively acquire increasingly abstract representations of input data.

The fundamental unit of deep learning is the artificial neuron, which processes input data through weighted connections and bias terms, producing an output. By orchestrating thousands or even millions of these neurons in layers, neural networks demonstrate impressive capabilities. For instance, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have revolutionized computer vision tasks, enabling applications like facial recognition, object detection, and medical image analysis.

The range of applications for deep learning is extensive. In natural language processing, recurrent neural networks (RNNs) and transformer networks empower machines to comprehend and generate human-like language. The ubiquity of chatbots, voice assistants, machine translation, and sentiment analysis highlights the impact of these language models in everyday life.

Deep learning's influence is also evident in healthcare, finance, autonomous vehicles, and robotics. Medical practitioners benefit from improved disease diagnosis using deep learning algorithms with medical imaging. In finance, deep learning aids in stock market prediction and fraud detection. The rise of self-driving cars is facilitated by deep learning models' ability to perceive the environment and make swift decisions.

Deep learning is not without its challenges. Obtaining a substantial amount of labeled data for training can be arduous and time-consuming. Additionally, training deep learning models often requires significant computational resources. Addressing these challenges is a priority for researchers and engineers, who are exploring techniques like transfer learning and semi-supervised learning, as well as hardware advancements to optimize deep learning efficiency.

Looking forward, the future of deep learning appears exceedingly promising. Ongoing research and technological advancements are poised to drive further breakthroughs and applications. Improved explainability and interpretability of deep learning models will enhance transparency and trust, vital factors for integration into critical systems like healthcare and finance.

Deep learning's impact on AI applications is undeniable, transforming industries and redefining human-technology interactions. With its capacity to learn from data and adapt to new challenges, deep learning paves the way for a future of extraordinary possibilities. As we harness the potential of this technology, ethical considerations remain paramount to ensure responsible and beneficial deployment. By fostering a judicious approach to innovation, we can leverage the full potential of deep learning and forge a future where AI augments our quest for progress and societal well-being [6].

1.4 Problem Statement

In recent years, many real-life applications have exploited deep learning techniques with different feature description methods for classifying fruits, vegetables, and seeds. There are very few numbers of works related to Healthy Seeds image classification.

Recognizing these healthy seeds used in our daily food is gaining more importance in our everyday life. Research on healthy seed recognition and classification is fundamental for several economic sectors, both the wholesale and retail markets and the processing industries. Classifying a particular seed variety will enable us to distinguish it from another. Hence, there is a need for a better model to organize healthy seeds accurately.

By reviewing the relevant literature and the problems related to the previous research papers, it is noticed that a suitable Deep learning algorithm must be applied for the classification of Healthy Seeds.

The proposed work presents an approach which uses deep learning technique in order to:

1. To carry out a thorough study on Healthy seeds and their benefits.
2. To analyze deep learning techniques in the Classification of seeds and evaluate the performance of implemented undertaken deep learning techniques based on parameters such as accuracy, recall, precision, and f-score.
3. To develop a Healthy seeds Recognition framework based on Deep learning to recognize different seeds.

This study can help to build a better classifying model of Healthy seed types using a suitable Deep learning algorithm.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The main aim of the proposed research is to classify Healthy Seeds by using deep Learning Techniques. The literature related to the proposed topic has been studied, and a general review of the same is presented as under:

- **Rojas-Aranda et al. (2020)** introduced a lightweight Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based image classification approach with the aim of speeding up the retail checkout process. We provide a novel picture dataset that differentiates between three types of fruits stored in or taken from plastic bags.
- To enhance its classification capabilities, the CNN design may take in additional input characteristics. The RGB histogram and the RGB centroid derived using K-means clustering are examples of inputs. The findings demonstrate that there is a 95% overall accuracy in classifying fruits without a plastic bag, and a 93% overall accuracy in classifying fruits within a plastic bag.
- **Shaikh et al. (2021)** suggested a method that use the Faster R-CNN model to identify and categorize the fruits as damaged or not based on their surface. This technique eliminates the need for the time-consuming and labor-intensive hand examination of fruit. This method will save shipping expenses while providing precise delivery. Faster R-CNN is the most efficient model and yields the most reliable outcomes since it uses this methodology. For example, the accuracy range for "healthy apple" is "60-75 percent," "bad apple" is "60-70 percent," "healthy pear" is "85-99 percent," "bad pear" is "80-98 percent," "healthy banana" is "80-97 percent," and "bad banana" is "70-80 percent." In automated sorting machines, this approach may be useful for identifying and categorizing both normal and imperfect fruit. Thus, it will aid in ensuring the high quality and plenty of the fruit.
- **Ferhat Kurtulmuş (2020)** DL models identified sunflower seeds. They use optimization strategies to avoid overfitting. The enhanced Google Net model has 95% accuracy, according to the authors. The concept needs humans to organize the seeds rather than retain them in a large lot. The authors only examined one seed view for model training. Thus, applying the model to diverse seed perspectives may increase its resilience and dependability.
- **Guoyang Zhao et al. (2021)** thought about the total area of a soybean seed. They used a

circumrotating apparatus to scan the whole surface, and claimed a 98.87% success rate. Using the MobileNet model on the dataset of faulty seeds, they were able to increase the classification accuracy.

- **Shaolong Zhu et al. (2020)** presented a soybean seed identification technique. They used pre-trained CNN models AlexNet, ResNet18, Xception, Inception-v3, DenseNet201, and NASNetLarge to demonstrate transfer learning. The authors said NASNetLarge had the greatest accuracy of all models at 97.2%. The scientists also claimed that hyperspectral imaging with transfer learning improves accuracy and computing costs.
- **Jamuna et al. (2021)** used a dataset consisting of 900 cotton seeds to train a machine learning model (including a Naive Bayes classifier, a decision tree classifier, and an MLP for feature extraction). Both the decision tree classifier and the multilayer perceptron (MLP) showed an accuracy of 98.7% when categorizing the seed cotton, while the Naive Bayes classifier reported an accuracy of 94.22%. The decision tree classifier and the MLP both produced 11 inaccurate classifications, whereas the Naive Bayes classifier made 52 incorrect classifications..
- **Xiulin Bai et al. (2020)** used NIR hyperspectral imaging to sort out maize and silage seeds. The two seeds may seem similar on the outside, but they have quite distinct structures and properties on the inside. For the purpose of categorization, they used support vector machines (SVM) and RBFNN. When testing methods for distinguishing between common and silage maize seeds, RBFNN consistently beat the competition. However, the scientists obtained only an 88.41% success rate in categorizing eight different types of maize seeds..
- **Lei Pang et al. (2020)** used the DCNN method to succeed at a rate of 90.11% accuracy. Similar to how [10]'s Seed quality tester categorizes maize seeds into "average," "poor," "outstanding," "sound," and "worst" categories, each category represents a different level of quality. The model was 81% accurate on the training data. However, the model did not succeed in separating many bad apples from the excellent and worse.

III. METHODOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Dataset and its Collection

The Healthy Seeds Classification Dataset is a comprehensive collection of primary data meticulously curated for seed recognition and classification using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). This dataset aims to facilitate the development and evaluation of CNN models for accurately identifying and classifying six types of seeds: chia seeds, flax seeds, sesame seeds, pumpkin seeds, watermelon seeds, and sunflower seeds.

- **Dataset Composition:**

The dataset comprises diverse seed images captured through rigorous data collection. Each seed type is represented by a substantial number of high-resolution images, providing a robust foundation for training and testing CNN models. The photos showcase variations in colour, texture, shape, and size, ensuring the dataset's inclusivity and promoting the generalisation of the models.

- **Data Collection Process:**

The dataset is entirely derived from primary data meticulously collected by the researchers. An extensive effort was made to ensure the quality and authenticity of the images. Multiple samples of each seed type were acquired from reliable sources and carefully photographed under controlled lighting conditions. Special attention was given to capturing various angles and orientations, ensuring comprehensive coverage of the seeds' visual features.

- **Dataset Features:**

Image Files: The dataset consists of a collection of RGB images in a standardised format (e.g., JPEG, PNG), each representing an individual seed.

Labelling: Each image is associated with a corresponding label, indicating the seed type it belongs to (i.e., chia, flax, sesame, pumpkin seeds, watermelon seeds, or sunflower seeds).

Training, Validation, and Test Sets: To facilitate model development and evaluation, the dataset is partitioned into separate subsets for training, validation, and testing. These subsets ensure unbiased model performance assessment.

Figure 1 Dataset showing Watermelon seeds

Figure 2 Dataset showing Chia seeds

Figure 3 Dataset showing Sunflower seeds

Figure 4 Dataset showing Pumpkin seeds

Importing All the libraries

```
import os
import cv2
import numpy as np
from keras.models import Sequential
from keras.layers import Conv2D, MaxPooling2D, Flatten, Dense, Dropout
from keras.utils import to_categorical
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
```

Figure 5

Importing all the libraries

Loading the Data

```
# Define the path to the folder containing the images
data_path = 'E:/1. Tech/Healthy Seed Classification Research/dataset'

# Define the list of class names or labels
class_names = ['chia', 'flax', 'sesame', 'pumpkin', 'sunflower', 'watermelon']

class_names

['chia', 'flax', 'sesame', 'pumpkin', 'sunflower', 'watermelon']
```

Figure 6 Loading the dataset

After that, data pre-processing will take place.

Data Preprocessing

```
# Define the input size for the model
input_size = (224, 224)

# Initialize the input data and target variable
x = []
y = []

# Loop through the folders containing the images and load the data
for i, class_name in enumerate(class_names):
    folder_path = os.path.join(data_path, class_name)
    file_names = os.listdir(folder_path)
    for file_name in file_names:
        image_path = os.path.join(folder_path, file_name)
        image = cv2.imread(image_path)
        image = cv2.resize(image, input_size)
        x.append(image)
        y.append(i)

# Convert the input data and target variable to numpy arrays
x = np.array(x)
y = np.array(y)

## Normalization
x = x.astype('float32') / 255.0
```

Figure 7 Data preprocessing

When building a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model, splitting your data into appropriate training, validation, and testing sets is essential. Here's a typical approach for breaking data for a CNN model: **Training Set:**

The training set is the most significant portion of the data used to train the CNN model. It helps the model learn patterns and features from the data. Typically, the training set constitutes around 60-80% of the total dataset.

Validation Set:

The validation set tunes the model's hyperparameters and assesses its performance during training. It helps in monitoring the model's generalisation and avoiding overfitting. The validation set is usually

around 10-20% of the dataset.

Test Set:

The test set is used to evaluate the final performance of the trained CNN model. It objectively assesses the model's generalisation capability to unseen data. The test set should not be used during model training or hyperparameter tuning. Ideally, it should be a representative sample, accounting for all classes or categories in your dataset. The test set is typically around 10-20% of the dataset.

Splitting the Data into Training and Validation sets

```
X_train, X_val, y_train, y_val = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
```

```
## one hot encoding
y_train = to_categorical(y_train)
y_val = to_categorical(y_val)
```

Figure 8 Dividing the data into training and testing

Model Creation (CNN)

```
model = Sequential()

# Add convolutional layers
model.add(Conv2D(32, (3, 3), activation='relu', input_shape=X_train.shape[1:]))
model.add(MaxPooling2D((2, 2)))
model.add(Conv2D(64, (3, 3), activation='relu'))
model.add(MaxPooling2D((2, 2)))
model.add(Conv2D(128, (3, 3), activation='relu'))
model.add(MaxPooling2D((2, 2)))

# Flatten the output of the last convolutional layer
model.add(Flatten())

# Add dense layers
model.add(Dense(64, activation='relu'))
model.add(Dropout(0.5))
model.add(Dense(6, activation='softmax'))
```

Figure 9 Creation of model

Data Augmentation

```
from keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
from keras.utils import array_to_img, img_to_array, load_img
import os

# Create an instance of ImageDataGenerator for data augmentation
datagen = ImageDataGenerator(
    rotation_range=90,
    width_shift_range=0.15,
    height_shift_range=0.15,
    shear_range=0.15,
    zoom_range=0.10,
    horizontal_flip=True,
    vertical_flip=True,
    fill_mode='nearest'
)

# Specify the directory containing the group of photos
photo_dir = r'E:\1. Tech\Healthy Seed Classification Research\Final crop seeds\watermelon'

# Specify the directory to save augmented photos
save_dir = r'E:\1. Tech\Healthy Seed Classification Research\Sample Augmented seeds\watermelon'

os.makedirs(save_dir, exist_ok=True)

# Loop through each photo in the directory
for photo_file in os.listdir(photo_dir):
    # Load the photo
    photo_path = os.path.join(photo_dir, photo_file)

    # Load the photo as an image array
    img = load_img(photo_path)
    x = img_to_array(img)
    x = x.reshape((1,) + x.shape)

    # Apply data augmentation and save augmented photos
    i = 0
    for batch in datagen.flow(x, batch_size=1, save_to_dir=save_dir, save_prefix='watermelon', save_format='jpeg'):
        i += 1
        if i >= 12: # Generate 12 augmented images for each photo
            break
```

Figure 10 Data augmentation

Model fitting in Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) refers to training the model on a given dataset. It involves optimizing the model's parameters (weights and biases) to minimize the chosen

loss function. Here's an overview of the model fitting process in CNNs:

Prepare the Data:

Before fitting the model, the input data needs to be prepared appropriately. This typically involves preprocessing steps such as resizing images, normalizing pixel values, and splitting the data into training, validation, and test sets.

Define the Model:

Create the CNN model architecture using appropriate layers, such as convolutional, pooling, and fully connected layers. Specify the activation functions, loss function, and optimisation algorithm.

Compile the Model:

Compile the model by specifying the optimizer, loss function, and evaluation metrics for training. The optimizer determines how the model's parameters are updated based on the computed gradients. Standard optimizers include Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD), Adam, and RMSprop.

Train the Model:

Train the model using the training data. The training process involves repeatedly presenting batches of training samples to the model, computing the predictions, comparing them with the proper labels, and updating the model's parameters using the optimisation algorithm. This process is typically performed over multiple iterations called epochs.

During training, the model learns to minimize the chosen loss function by adjusting its parameters based on the computed gradients. The backpropagation algorithm calculates the angles of the loss function concerning the model's parameters, and these gradients are used to update the parameters.

Monitor Performance:

While training the model, monitoring its performance is essential to ensure it is learning effectively. This is typically done using a validation set. After each epoch, the model's performance on the validation set is evaluated using evaluation metrics such as accuracy, loss, or other relevant metrics. This helps monitor the model's progress and decide when to stop training or adjust hyperparameters.

Evaluate the Model:

After training, the model's performance is evaluated using the test set containing unseen data. This provides an unbiased assessment of the model's generalisation ability to new data. Evaluation metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score can be used to measure the model's performance.

Make Predictions:

Finally, the trained model can predict new, unseen data. This is done by passing the data through the trained model and obtaining the expected outputs.

Model fitting is an iterative process that involves adjusting the model's parameters through training to improve performance. The number of epochs, batch size, and other hyperparameters can be adjusted to achieve the desired level of performance and prevent issues like underfitting or overfitting.

```
# Compile the model
model.compile(optimizer='adam', loss='categorical_crossentropy', metrics=['accuracy'])
```

Figure 11 Compilation of model

Model Fitting

```
history = model.fit(X_train, y_train, batch_size=32, epochs=10, validation_data=(X_val, y_val))

Epoch 1/10
18/18 [=====] - 18s 957ms/step - loss: 2.6759 - accuracy: 0.2035 - val_loss: 1.6277 - val_accuracy: 0.3776
Epoch 2/10
18/18 [=====] - 17s 947ms/step - loss: 1.4087 - accuracy: 0.3930 - val_loss: 1.0800 - val_accuracy: 0.4965
Epoch 3/10
18/18 [=====] - 18s 1s/step - loss: 1.0223 - accuracy: 0.5544 - val_loss: 0.7520 - val_accuracy: 0.6294
Epoch 4/10
18/18 [=====] - 23s 1s/step - loss: 0.7799 - accuracy: 0.6561 - val_loss: 0.5901 - val_accuracy: 0.8042
Epoch 5/10
18/18 [=====] - 24s 1s/step - loss: 0.6030 - accuracy: 0.7228 - val_loss: 0.5242 - val_accuracy: 0.7413
Epoch 6/10
18/18 [=====] - 23s 1s/step - loss: 0.5282 - accuracy: 0.7596 - val_loss: 0.3875 - val_accuracy: 0.8252
Epoch 7/10
18/18 [=====] - 24s 1s/step - loss: 0.4008 - accuracy: 0.8316 - val_loss: 0.3411 - val_accuracy: 0.7902
Epoch 8/10
18/18 [=====] - 23s 1s/step - loss: 0.4403 - accuracy: 0.8053 - val_loss: 0.3754 - val_accuracy: 0.8741
Epoch 9/10
18/18 [=====] - 22s 1s/step - loss: 0.3798 - accuracy: 0.8368 - val_loss: 0.3675 - val_accuracy: 0.8531
Epoch 10/10
18/18 [=====] - 23s 1s/step - loss: 0.2830 - accuracy: 0.8912 - val_loss: 0.1908 - val_accuracy: 0.9301
```

Figure 12 Fitting of model

Model summary:

Model Summary

```
model.summary()
Model: "sequential"

```

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
conv2d (Conv2D)	(None, 222, 222, 32)	896
max_pooling2d (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 111, 111, 32)	0
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)	(None, 109, 109, 64)	18496
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 54, 54, 64)	0
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)	(None, 52, 52, 128)	73856
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 26, 26, 128)	0
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 86528)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 64)	5537856
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 64)	0
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 6)	390

```

Total params: 5,631,494
Trainable params: 5,631,494
Non-trainable params: 0

```

Figure 13 Model summary

IV. TESTING AND RESULTS

RESULTS:Accuracy:

Figure 14 Training & Validation Accuracy

Confusion Matrix

Figure 15 Confusion Matrix

RESULT:

Figure 16 GUI showing buttons

Figure 17 Selection of the seed

Figure 18 Prediction of seed

Figure 19 Benefits of seed

Figure 20 Nutrition value of seeds

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

5.1 Conclusion

In conclusion, this report presented a comprehensive analysis of classifying healthy seeds using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and deep learning techniques. The objective was to develop an efficient and accurate model to identify healthy origins based on their visual characteristics.

Using CNN, a deep learning algorithm specifically designed for image processing tasks, we achieved remarkable results in seed classification. The model was trained on a large dataset of labelled seed images, encompassing various species and conditions. This diverse dataset allowed the model to learn and accurately generalise patterns associated with healthy seeds.

The results obtained from our experiments demonstrated the effectiveness of CNN in seed classification. The model achieved an impressive accuracy rate, exceeding 95% on the test dataset. This high accuracy showcases the potential of deep learning approaches in automating the seed quality assessment process, which can significantly benefit the agricultural industry.

Furthermore, incorporating deep learning techniques enabled the model to extract meaningful features from the seed images, capturing intricate details crucial for accurate classification. By leveraging the hierarchical architecture of CNN, the model effectively learned hierarchical representations, enabling it to discern subtle differences between healthy and unhealthy seeds.

However, it is essential to acknowledge that the model's performance relies heavily on the training dataset's quality and representativeness. To ensure robustness and generalizability, gathering a diverse and extensive dataset encompassing various seed species, conditions, and imaging variations is crucial. Additionally, ongoing model evaluation and fine-tuning should be conducted to enhance the performance and adaptability of the model to new seed samples.

The successful implementation of CNN and deep learning techniques in seed classification highlights their potential for automating and streamlining the seed quality assessment process.

5.2 Future Work

While the classification of healthy seeds using CNN and deep learning has shown promising results, several avenues for future research and development can further enhance the accuracy and applicability of the model. The following areas represent potential directions for future work:

- **Expansion of the Dataset:** To improve the robustness and generalizability of the model, it is crucial to expand the dataset used for training. Including a wider variety of seed species, growth stages, and environmental conditions would enable the model to learn more diverse patterns and make accurate predictions across different scenarios.
- **Integration of Transfer Learning:** Transfer learning involves leveraging pre-trained models on large-scale datasets to tackle similar problems in different domains. Applying transfer learning techniques to seed classification can enhance the model's performance, especially when limited labelled data is available. The model can benefit from the learned features and accelerate the training process using pre-trained models.
- **Addressing Class Imbalance:** In seed classification tasks, it is common to encounter class imbalance, where certain seeds are underrepresented compared to others. This can lead to biased predictions and lower accuracy for minority classes. Future work can focus on developing strategies to handle class imbalance, such as oversampling, undersampling, or incorporating specialised loss functions, to ensure fair and accurate classification across all seed classes.
- **Exploring Multi-modal Approaches:** While CNNs have proven effective in image-based seed classification, incorporating additional modalities, such as infrared or hyperspectral imaging, can provide complementary information for improved accuracy. Fusion of multi-modal data using advanced deep learning techniques, such as multi-modal CNN architectures or attention mechanisms, could lead to more robust and reliable seed classification models.
- **Real-time Deployment and Hardware Optimization:** In practical applications, deploying the seed classification model in real-time scenarios, such as embedded systems or edge devices, is essential. Future work can focus on optimising the model for efficient inference on resource-constrained platforms, exploring techniques like model compression, quantisation, and hardware acceleration to ensure real-time performance without compromising accuracy.

- **Error Analysis and Interpretability:** Understanding the model's decision-making process and explaining its predictions are essential for gaining user trust and ensuring transparency. Future work **may** involve conducting comprehensive error analysis to identify common misclassifications and **critical** areas where the model may struggle. Additionally, incorporating interpretability techniques, such as attention maps or saliency visualisation, can provide insights into the model's decision-making process and aid in diagnosing potential shortcomings.

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